

Supporting Information

Single site W(0)- vs Re(I)-dipyridophenazine based Conjugated Porous Polymer for CO₂ Photoreduction

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1. Materials

The reagents and solvents used, both in the synthesis of the ligands and organometallic complexes and in the polymers, were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich, Across organics and Alfa-Aesar. The solvents were used dry and deoxygenated and the reactions were carried out using Schlenk techniques under inert argon atmosphere.

2. Experimental methods

The experimental techniques used in the characterization of these compounds are as follows:

NMR ^1H - and ^{13}C - NMR spectra were recorded, unless otherwise indicated, at room temperature on a Bruker Avance spectrometer (300 MHz, ^1H and 75 MHz, ^{13}C) using CDCl_3 or DMSO as solvents. Solid state ^{13}C -CP/MAS NMR spectra of molecular samples were recorded with a BRUKER AVANCE III HD (Larmor frequencies of 400, 101 MHz for ^1H , ^{13}C) for liquids and a Bruker AV400 WB spectrometer (Larmor frequencies of 400 and 100 MHz) using 4 mm MAS probes spinning at 10 kHz rate for ^{13}C solid-state MAS-NMR measurements. The ^{13}C CP-MAS spectra were obtained using 3.5 ms contact time and 4 s relaxation time. The number of scans was 1024 of ^{13}C CP-MAS spectra.

FT-IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin Elmer 1650 FTIR spectrophotometer between 4000 and 400 cm^{-1} . The support used to prepare the samples was KBr and only the most significant bands are indicated.

MALDI-TOF (Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time of Flight) mass were recorded on a Bruker ULTRAREFLEX III TOF/TOF spectrophotometer equipped with a Neodymium Yag laser ($\lambda=355\text{ nm}$) in the reflector and positive linear modes. The **HR-MS** analysis was carried out by using an Agilent 1200 Series LC system coupled to a 6520 quadrupole-time of flight (QTOF) mass spectrometer. Acetonitrile: water (75:25, v:v) was used as mobile phase at 0.2 mL min^{-1} . The ionization source was an ESI interface working in the positive-ion mode.

SEM-EDX images were recorded on a FEI Nova NanoSEM 230 microscope, which incorporates an EDX detector that allows the identification of the elements.

Uv-Vis and diffuse reflectance (DRS) spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2401 PC UV-Visible spectrometer between 200 and 800 nm.

Adsorption-desorption isotherms were obtained at 77 K using a Quantachrome surface and porosity analyzer. Prior to measurement, the samples were degassed for 12 h at 100°C . Specific surface areas were determined by N_2 adsorption-desorption at 77K and the pore

distribution by DFT methods. Surface area was determined by the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) method.

Powder X-Ray Diffraction (PXRD) patterns were measured with a Bruker D8 diffractometer with a Sol-X energy dispersive detector, working at 40 kV and 30 mA and employing CuK α ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) filtered radiation. The diffractograms were registered with a step size of 0.1° and exposure time of 0.5 s per step and a 2θ range of $3\text{--}30^\circ$.

X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). XPS analyses were recorded on a lab-based spectrometer (SPECS GmbH, Berlin) using a monochromated AlK α 1 source ($h\nu = 1486.6 \text{ eV}$) operating at 50 W. In the spectrometer, the X-ray was focused with a μ -FOCUS 600 monochromator onto a $300 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ spot on the sample, and the data were recorded with a PHOIBOS 150 NAP 1D-DLD analyzer in a fixed analyzer transmission (FAT) mode. The pass energy was set to 40 eV for survey scans and 20 eV for high-resolution regions. The binding energy scale was calibrated using Au 4f $_{7/2}$ (84.01 eV) and Ag 3d $_{5/2}$ (368.20 eV). Recorded spectra were additionally calibrated against the C 1s internal reference. Data interpretation was done with CasaXPS. Shirley or two-point linear background was used depending on the spectrum shape. Surface chemical analysis was done based on the peak area of high-resolution spectra and the CasaXPS sensitivity factors (where RSF of C 1s = 1.000).

X-ray absorption (XAS). XAS spectra at Re and W K-edge were measured at the BL18 beamline at the Diamond synchrotron using a Si(111) and Si(311) double crystal monochromator for Re and W L3-edge, respectively. The beamline was calibrated with Re and W foils measured in transmission mode and the incident and transmitted photons acquired by two ionization chambers filled with different ratios of He/N $_2$ /Kr. The focus at the sample position was adjusted to be around $400 \times 400 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$. Measurements were performed in fluorescence mode. The samples were placed to 45° with respect to the incoming beam and the fluorescence signal collected by a six channels silicon drift detector placed to 90° to the incident beam. The data were analyzed by ATHENA and ARTEMIS software of the DEMETER package.

Electrochemical characterization. Cyclic voltammetry's were carried out in order to calculate the LUMO (Lowest occupied molecular orbital) energy levels of the materials (Vacuum, eV). LUMO level to the last reduction peak of the voltammetry. The reduction peak values obtained were corrected by the use of ferrocene redox couple and they were placed in *Error! Reference source not found.*:

$$E_{LUMO}(\text{eV}) = - \left[4.8 - E_{1/2}(\text{Fc}, \text{Fc}^+) + E_{red, onset} \right] \quad \text{Eq. S1}$$

The half-wave potential of the ferrocene/ferrocenium redox couple (Fc/Fc^+) was estimated from the *Eq.* :

$$E_{1/2}(Fc/Fc^+) = (E_{ap} + E_{cp}) / 2 \quad \text{Eq. S2}$$

Where E_{ap} and E_{cp} are the anodic and cathodic peak potentials, respectively.

The measurements were driven in a three-electrode cell configuration. Current and voltage signals were measured through an Autolab PGSTAT204 potentiostat/galvanostat station. The working electrode used was a platinum tip on which a polymeric or monomer ink prepared was deposited. The ink was prepared by mixing 5 mg of each CPP with 45 μ L of Nafion perfluorinated resin solution (5% wt. in mixture of lower aliphatic alcohols and water, 45%) and 450 μ L of isopropanol. After that, this ink was deposited and dried on the platinum working electrode. A platinum wire was used as the counter electrode and a Ag/AgCl electrode as the reference and then LUMO position was determined by calibrating with ferrocene. A 0.1 M of $[NBu_4]PF_6$ in propylene carbonate was utilized as electrolyte.

Theoretical calculations. Optoelectronics properties of CPP-W and CPP-Re were calculated using Time dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) [1,2] implemented in the software Gaussian 09 [3] employing a B3LYP functional [4,5,6] and def2tzvp[7,8] basis set. Moreover, a fix number of 100 states were selected for a proper comparison between all configurations and models.

3. Synthesis of Br₂W-and Br₂Re-precursors

3.1. Synthesis of 2,7-dibromodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine (1)

Scheme S1. Synthesis of phenanthroline precursor **1**.

A solution of 3,8-dibromo-1,10-phenanthroline-5,6-dione (228 mg, 0.620 mmol, 1.0 eq), o-phenylenediamine (89.8 mg, 0.830 mmol, 1.34 eq.) in anhydrous MeOH (30 mL) was prepared under inert atmosphere and stirred at reflux for 24 h. The resulting suspension is filtered in air and the precipitate was washed with MeOH and dried under vacuum. Compound **1** was isolated pure as a light-yellow solid stable in air and very insoluble in common organic solvents. Yield: 88%. IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): ν = 3021 (=CH), 1654 (C=N), 1561 (C=C), δ = 907 (CH out plane). ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆, 100°C, δ): 9.69 (m, H_{2,9}), 9.31 (m, H_{4,7}), 8.44 (m, H_{14,17}), 8.13 (m, H_{15,16}). ¹³C NMR (101 MHz, solid δ): 155.22, 144.44, 141.31, 138.12, 131.97, 129.53, 126.74, 123.88, 115.30. HRMS (*m/z*): 440.9166 (M+ H⁺), 462.8991 (M⁺ Na⁺). Elemental analysis for C₁₈H₈Br₂N₄ calc.: C, 49.12; H, 1.83; N, 12.73 %; found: C, 48.70; H, 2.28; N, 12.23 %.

Compound **1** results insoluble in most organic solvents and only a poor ¹H-NMR spectrum was obtained in DMSO(d₆) at 100 °C (**Figure S1**), therefore the ¹³C-NMR solid state spectrum was recorded, (**Figure S2**) confirming that compound was effectively obtained. ¹H-NMR spectrum shows signals at 9.69, 9.31 ppm (phenanthroline core) and 8.44, 8.13 ppm assigned to phenyl ring (**Figure S1**). ¹³C-NMR solid state spectrum shows 9 signals with the characteristic imine signal at 155.2 ppm and the consequent absence of the carbonyl signal from the starting precursor (**Figure S2**). Therefore, the high-resolution mass spectrum showed two peaks corresponding to the ion (M+ H⁺) and (M+ Na⁺) whose experimental isotopic distribution coincides with the theoretical one (**Figure S3**). By FTIR was checked the disappearance of carbonyl groups (ca. 1657 cm⁻¹) and also the presence of -C=N- stretching band located at 1654 cm⁻¹ (**Figure S4**).

Figure S1. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (DMSO- d_6 , 100°C)

Figure S2. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (CPMAS solid).

Figure S3. HR-MS spectrum.

Figure S4. FT-IR spectrum

3.2. Synthesis of $\text{Re}(\text{CO})_5\text{Br}$ [9]

In a 100 mL flask, under inert atmosphere, $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ (500 mg, 0.766 mmol, 0.9 eq.) and 20 mL of dry, deoxygenated hexane are added. The solution is purged with Ar for 20 min, and then Br_2 (43.6 μL , 0.851 mmol, 1.0 eq.) is gradually added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 30 min. During the course of the reaction a white precipitate is observed to form which is filtered off under inert atmosphere, washed with hexane and dried under vacuum. The $\text{Re}(\text{CO})_5\text{Br}$ complex is isolated pure as a white solid which is stored under inert atmosphere. Yield: 98% **IR (KBr, cm^{-1})**: ν_{CO} 2154 (d), 2046 (f) and 1988 (m)

Figure S5. FT-IR in DCM of $\text{Re}_2(\text{CO})_{10}$ (red) and $\text{Re}(\text{CO})_5\text{Br}$ (black)

3.3. - Synthesis of Re- and W-organometallic monomers (2 and 3)

3.3.1.- Synthesis of 2,7-dibromodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine- $\text{W}(\text{CO})_4$ (2)

To a 100 mL two-necked flask under inert atmosphere, compound **1** (150 mg, 0.341 mmol, 1.0 eq.), $\text{W}(\text{CO})_6$ (132 mg, 0.375 mmol, 1.1 eq.) and 10 mL of xylene were added. The resulting mixture was purged with Ar for 20 minutes and then kept under stirring at reflux for 18 hours. After reaching room temperature, the suspension was filtered under inert atmosphere and the precipitate was washed with diethyl ether and dried under vacuum. Compound **2** was isolated pure as an air-stable beige solid, poorly soluble in common organic solvents. Yield: 66% FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}): ν 3021 (=CH), 2006, 1901 (sh), 1888, 1823 (CO), 1654 (C=N), 1562 (C=C), δ 907 (CH out plane). ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 δ): 9.82 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 2H, $\text{H}_{2,9}$), 9.30 (d, $J = 2.3$ Hz, 2H, $\text{H}_{4,7}$), 8.40 (dd, $J = 6.5, 3.5$ Hz, 2H, $\text{H}_{14,17}$), 8.00 (dd, $J = 6.5, 3.5$ Hz, 2H, $\text{H}_{15,16}$). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, solid, δ): 213.11 (CO), 200.89 (CO), 154.91, 144.84, 141.47, 138.42, 132.07, 130.19, 126.79, 123.96, 116.00. Elemental analysis for

$C_{18}H_8Br_2N_4$ calc.: C, 49.12; H, 1.83; N, 12.73 %; found: C, 48.70; H, 2.28; N, 12.23 %. MS (MALDI, m/z): 707.9 ($M^+ - CO$).

Figure S6.- 1H NMR (left) and ^{13}C -NMR (right) spectra.

Figure S7.- MALDI Mass spectrum (calculated and found) and FTIR spectrum.

3.3.2.- Synthesis of 2,7-dibromodipyrido[3,2-a:2',3'-c]phenazine- $Re(CO)_3Br$ (**3**)

To a 100 mL two-necked flask under inert atmosphere, compound **1** (136 mg, 0.309 mmol, 1.0 eq.), $Re(CO)_5Br$ (115 mg, 0.283 mmol, 1.0 eq.) and 20 mL of toluene are added. The resulting mixture is purged with Ar for 20 minutes and then kept under stirring at reflux for 21 hours. After reaching room temperature, the suspension is filtered under inert atmosphere and the precipitate is washed with toluene and diethyl ether and dried under vacuum. Compound **3** is isolated pure as an air-stable orange-red solid, poorly soluble in common organic solvents. Yield: 97% FTIR (KBr, cm^{-1}): $\nu = 3010$ ($=CH$), 2026, 1917, 1901 (CO), 1639 (C=N), 1572 (C=C), δ 909 (CH out plane). 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$ δ): 9.95 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 2H, $H_{2,9}$), 9.47 (d, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 2H, $H_{4,7}$), 8.47 (dd, $J = 6.5, 3.5$ Hz, 2H, $H_{14,17}$), 8.11 (dd, $J = 6.5, 3.5$ Hz, 2H, $H_{15,16}$). ^{13}C NMR (101 MHz, solid δ): 198.97 (CO), 188.95 (CO), 156.23, 146.48, 142.96, 137.23, 130.19, 125.99, 123.10, 120.0, 111.28. MS (MALDI, m/z): 789.8 (M^+).

Figure S8.- ^1H NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectra of compound **3.**

Figure S9.- MALDI MS (calc. and found) (left) and FTIR spectra (right) of compound **3.**

4.- Synthesis and characterization of Conjugated Porous Polymers based on W and Re (CPP-W, CPP-Re)

Figure S10. PXRD patterns of CPP-W (green) and CPP-Re (pink)

Table S1. Elemental analysis

		C (%)	H (%)	N (%)	M (%)
(C₂₄H₁₈)(C₁₂H₁₀)_{1.4}(C₂₂H₁₀N₄O₄W)_{0.1}					
CPP-W	Calc.	89.03	5.73	0.97	3.17
	Found	85.74	5.31	0.75	3.00
(C₂₄H₁₈)(C₁₂H₁₀)_{1.4}(C₂₁H₁₀N₄O₃BrRe)_{0.1}					
CPP-Re	Calc.	88.0	5.68	0.96	3.18
	Found	80.23	5.65	0.87	3.90
(C₂₄H₁₈)(C₁₂H₁₀)_{1.0}(C₂₁H₁₀N₄O₃BrRe)_{0.5}					
CPPRe1	Calc.	71.89	4.28	3.61	11.98
	Found	64.40	4.32	3.17	11.0

Figure S11. FT-IR (left) and ^{13}C -NMR (right) spectra of CPPs

Table S2. Porous properties of polymers

Entry	Material	Metal (%) ^a	S_{BET} (m^2/g) ^b	V ($\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$) ^c	Pore size (nm)
1	CPP-W	3.0	18	0.039	7.2
2	CPP-Re	3.9	211	0.25	7.5
3	CPP-Re1	11.0	195	0.26	4.9

^aCalculated by ICP. ^bAt P/Po: 0.99; ^cCalculated from the nitrogen adsorption isotherm.

Figure S12. N_2 -DFT pore distribution.

Figure S13. Thermal analysis of CPP-Re1

Figure S14. EDX analysis of CPP-Re

Figure S15. EDX analysis of CPP-W

Figure S16. XPS spectra wide scan of (a) CPP-Re and (b) CPP-W. Note that CPP-Re exhibits peaks relative to the presence of Cs, probably due to the experimental procedure.

Figure S17. Solid state UV-vis absorption and diffuse reflectance spectra. Note that the absorption profile of both Re based materials is almost the same

Figure S18. Solid state diffuse reflectance spectra of CPP-W (green) and CPP-Re (pink)

Table S3. Vertical transition for CPP-Re calculated by TD DFT

Wavelength (nm)	Osc. Stench	Main contribution
678.9	6E-4	HOMO->LUMO (98%)
658.0	0.0047	H-1->LUMO (99%)
592.7	7E-4	HOMO->L+1 (98%)
556.1	0.0279	H-1->L+1 (97%)
504.5	7E-4	H-2->LUMO (99%)
502.3	0.0071	HOMO->L+2 (98%)
490.3	0.0036	H-1->L+2 (95%)
488.9	0.0098	H-3->LUMO (94%)
484.6	6E-4	H-4->LUMO (97%)
446.9	1E-4	H-4->L+1 (96%)
434.2	0.0563	H-5->LUMO (82%)
424.1	0.0072	H-2->L+1 (98%)
418.1	0.0077	H-8->LUMO (36%), H-7->LUMO (61%)
413.8	0.0099	H-8->LUMO (55%), H-7->LUMO (30%), H-5->LUMO (10%)
412.3	0.0625	H-3->L+1 (96%)
391.1	0.002	H-6->LUMO (92%)
385.9	0.001	H-2->L+2 (97%)
384.0	0.048	H-7->L+1 (64%), H-5->L+1 (19%)
380.1	0.001	H-22->LUMO (87%)
377.2	0.0091	H-3->L+2 (88%)
372.0	0.1124	H-8->L+1 (73%)
369.0	0.4535	H-7->L+1 (26%), H-5->L+1 (58%)
367.9	0.0046	H-17->LUMO (26%), H-9->LUMO (63%)
357.9	0.024	H-16->LUMO (77%), HOMO->L+4 (10%)
356.6	0.0088	H-16->L (12%), HOMO->L+4 (70%), HOMO->L+5 (11%)
350.1	0.017	H-17->LUMO (46%), H-9->LUMO (21%), H-1->L+4 (15%)
349.0	0.0097	H-1->L+4 (62%), H-1->L+5 (10%)
346.0	0.0432	H-7->L+2 (13%), H-5->L+2 (44%)
342.3	0.0077	H-8->L+2 (22%), H-7->L+2 (18%), H-6->L+1 (47%)
340.3	0.1068	H-8->L+2 (19%), H-7->L+2 (27%), H-6->L+1 (43%)
339.0	0.0183	H-20->LU (11%), H-8->L+2 (37%), H-7->L+2 (26%), H-5->L+2 (13%)
332.9	6E-4	HOMO->L+3 (99%)
328.8	0.1214	H-20->LUMO (51%), H-17->L+2 (14%), H-5->L+2 (18%)
327.4	0.0014	H-1->L+3 (99%)
323.6	0.0181	H-16->L+1 (84%)
321.5	0.9454	H-9->L+1 (30%), H-3->L+3 (11%), H-2->L+3 (23%)
320.9	0.5063	H-19->LUMO (53%)
320.0	0.6121	H-19->LUMO (42%), H-9->L+1 (11%), H-3->L+3 (12%)
319.2	0.0515	HOMO->L+4 (11%), HOMO->L+5 (44%), HOMO->L+6 (25%)
317.7	0.0053	H-3->L+3 (10%), H-2->L+4 (52%)
316.39	0.1368	H-21->L (35%), H-18->LUMO (13%), H-9->L+1 (14%)
315.60187	0.0212	H-6->L+2 (80%)
315.19268	0.0274	H-1->L+5 (16%), H-1->L+6 (41%), H-1->L+13 (14%)

Table S4. Vertical transition for CPP-W calculated by TD DFT

Wavelength (nm)	Osc. Stench	Main contribution
978.6	1E-4	HOMO->LUMO (98%)
824.8	4E-4	H-1->LUMO (22%), HOMO->L+1 (73%)
824.2	0.0015	H-1->LUMO (67%), HOMO->L+1 (24%)
810.7	6E-4	H-2->LUMO (89%)
689.76	0.0025	H-2->L+1 (85%), H-1->L+1 (12%)
598	0.0658	H-2->L+2 (28%), H-1->L+1 (59%)
556.6	0.0283	H-1->L+2 (95%)
546.2	0.1028	H-2->L+2 (70%), H-1->L+1 (25%)
496.5	1E-4	H-3->LUMO (99%)
475.9	0.0086	H-4->LUMO (97%)
429.3	0.0067	HOMO->L+4 (53%), HOMO->L+5 (15%), HOMO->L+7 (18%)
428.5	0.0531	H-5->LUMO (82%)
425.4	0.0044	HOMO->L+4 (16%), HOMO->L+7 (76%)
413.9	0.0031	H-3->L+1 (98%)
407.8	2E-4	H-2->L+7 (12%), H-1->L+7 (85%)
398.6	0.0828	H-4->L+1 (95%)
390.8	7E-4	H-2->L+4 (72%), H-2->L+5 (19%)
389.2	4E-4	HOMO->L+11 (96%)
388.4	0.0103	H-2->L+7 (45%), H-1->L+4 (12%), H-1->L+11 (25%)
386.8	0.001	H-6->LUMO (93%)
384.2	0.0431	H-1->L+4 (65%), H-1->L+5 (13%)
380.2	1E-4	HOMO->L+4 (21%), HOMO->L+5 (62%)
379.7	0.001	H-19->LUMO (75%), H-18->LUMO (14%)
378.9	3E-4	H-3->L+2 (98%)
376.4	2E-4	H-2->L+11 (82%), H-1->L+11 (13%)
369.7	1E-4	HOMO->L+6 (88%)
367.6	0.0574	H-4->L+2 (76%)
367.3	1E-4	H-1->L+3 (98%)
365.0	0.0687	H-13->LUMO (10%), H-12->LUMO (12%), H-7->LUMO (53%), H-5->L+1 (12%)
364.2	0.5977	H-5->L+1 (68%), H-4->L+2 (14%)
350.7	0.0062	H-1->L+4 (16%), H-1->L+5 (59%)
350.4	1E-4	HOMO->L+8 (75%)
350.3	0.0056	H-2->L+4 (18%), H-2->L+5 (54%), HOMO->L+8 (10%)
347.7	0.0168	H-13->LUMO (20%), H-12->LUMO (23%), H-7->LUMO (23%), H-5->L+2 (13%)
344.2	0.0161	H-15->LUMO (19%), H-5->L+2 (32%), H-1->L+6 (10%)
341.8	0.0537	H-1->L+6 (71%)
337.1	0.0271	H-2->L+6 (53%), HOMO->L+9 (16%), HOMO->L+10 (17%)
336.6	0.0177	H-2->L+6 (27%), HOMO->L+9 (31%), HOMO->L+10 (33%)
334.9	0.0416	H-6->L+1 (91%)
329.7	0.1952	H-15->LUMO (43%), H-5->L+2 (35%)
326.5	6E-4	H-2->L+8 (12%), H-1->L+8 (68%)

Figure S19. Selected molecular orbitals contributing vertical electronic transitions for CPP-W around 365 nm. Atom colour: C (Grey), O (Red), H (White), N (dark Blue), W (light blue).

Figure S20. Selected molecular orbitals contributing vertical electronic transitions for CPP-Re around 365 nm. Atom colour: C (Grey), O (Red), H (White), N (dark Blue), W (light blue).

Figure S21: Emission spectra of the irradiation source used in the photocatalytic tests: UV lamps (four 6W lamps, $\lambda_{\text{max}}=369$ nm, average intensity of 47.23Wm^{-2}).

Figure S22. Production rates ($\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$) of CPP-Re (a) and CPP-W (b) in the photocatalytic reduction of CO_2 with H_2O vapor under UV illumination. The error bars are estimated as 5%

Figure S23. Chromatograms from FID-A detector at different reaction times for CPP-W as photocatalyst.

Figure S24. Chromatograms from FID-B detector at different reaction times for CPP-W as photocatalyst.

Figure S25. FT-IR after CO₂PRR

Table S5. More relevant result regarding CO₂PRR by means the use of Porous organic polymers such as CPPs, CTFs or COFs and others inorganic photocatalyst used as benchmark^a

Catalyst	Reaction conditions	Light source	Products	Ref.
CPP-W	Solid phase, Continuous	6W lamps, $\lambda_{\max}=369$ nm, 47.23Wm^{-2}	CH₄: 4.8 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{metal}}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ C₂H₆: 11.4 $\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{metal}}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	This work
Ru@TpBpy	15 mg photocatalyst, 100 mL MeCN, 10 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp 800 nm $\geq \lambda \geq 420$ nm	HCOOH: 172 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[10]
Cu-COF	5 mg photocatalyst, 8 mL MeCN, 2 mL H ₂ O, 2 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420$ nm	CO: 206 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ H ₂ : 14 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[11]
Pt-SA/CTF-1	10 mg photocatalyst, 10 mL H ₂ O, 2.075 mL TEA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420$ nm	CH ₄ : 4.7 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CO: 1.4 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[12]
COF-367-Co(II)	10 mg photocatalyst, 20 mL MeCN, 2 mL TEA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda = 380$ nm	HCOOH: 48.6 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CO: 16.5 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CH ₄ : 12.8 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[13]
COF-367-Co(III)	10 mg photocatalyst, 20 mL MeCN, 2 mL TEA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda = 380$ nm	HCOOH: 93.0 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CO: 5.5 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CH ₄ : 10.1 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[13]
Ru/TpPa-1	10 mg photocatalyst, 100 mL MeCN, 10 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp 800 nm $\geq \lambda \geq 420$ nm	HCOOH: 108.8 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[14]
CT-COF	50 mg photocatalyst, 5 mL H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420$ nm	CO: 102.7 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[15]
TpBpy	15 mg photocatalyst, 100 mL MeCN, 10 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp 800 nm $\geq \lambda \geq 420$ nm	HCOOH: 102 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[10]
ACOF-1	10 mg photocatalyst, 5 mL H ₂ O	500 W Xe lamp 800 nm $\geq \lambda \geq 420$ nm	CH ₃ OH: 0.36 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[16]
N ₃ -COF	10 mg photocatalyst, 5 mL H ₂ O	500 W Xe lamp 800 nm $\geq \lambda \geq 420$ nm	CH ₃ OH: 0.57 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[16]
Re-Bpy-sp ² c-COF	1 mg photocatalyst, 4.83 mL MeCN, 0.16 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420$ nm	CO: 1040 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ H ₂ : 244 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[17]
Re-CTF-py	2 mg photocatalyst, 2 mL MeCN/TEOA (4/1)	300 W Xe lamp in the full light region	CO: 305 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[18]
Re@TEB-BPY	1.0 mg photocatalyst, MeCN/H ₂ O TEA (3:1:1) and BNAH	300 W Xe lamp; $\lambda=400-750$ nm visible band pass filter	CH ₄ : 2.05 mmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹	[19]
TTCOF-Zn	100 mg photocatalyst, 80 mL H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp 800 nm $\geq \lambda \geq 420$ nm	CO: 12.3 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[20]
PD-COF-23	2.5 mg photocatalyst, 3 mL MeCN, 2 mL H ₂ O, 0.5 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda = 420$ nm	CO: 20.9 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[21]
PD-COF-23-Ni	2.5 mg photocatalyst, 3 mL MeCN, 2 mL H ₂ O, 0.5 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda = 420$ nm	CO: 40.0 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[21]
NAHN-Tp	10 mg photocatalyst, 5 mL MeCN, 1 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420$ nm	CO: 88.6 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[22]
Imine-CTF	20 mg photocatalyst, 20 mL H ₂ O, 2 mL TEOA	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420$ nm	CH ₄ : 7.10 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CO: 5.90 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[23]
Mo-COF	10 mg photocatalyst, 5 mL H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420$ nm	CO: 6.19 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[24]
PdIn@N ₃ -COF	2 mg photocatalyst, 10 mL ultrapure H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 400$ nm	CH ₃ OH: 24.58 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CH ₃ CH ₂ OH: 8.63 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[25]
CTF-BP	20 mg photocatalyst, 30 mL MeCN, 10 mL TEOA, 10 mL H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda > 420$ nm	CH ₄ : 7.81 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CO: 4.60 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[26]
Re-f-COF	3.0 mL of CH ₃ CN, 0.2 mL of triethanolamine (TEOA), and 1.0 mg of Re-COF	Xe lamp with a cut off filter (>420 nm)	CO: 0.79 mmol g ⁻¹ h ⁻¹	[27] ¹

Re@TEB-BPY	acetonitrile–water mixture (3:1) as the solvent, and BNAH and TEA employed	visible light irradiation (400–750 nm) using	CO: 91.7 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[28]
Re-Bpy-sp2c-COF	acetonitrile (MeCN) and triethanolamine (TEOA) in 30 : 1 ratio	$\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$, 300 W Xe light source	CO: 1040 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[29]
Re-COF	3 mL acetonitrile (MeCN) and 0.2 mL triethanolamine (TEOA)	$\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$, 300 W Xe light source	CO: 750 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[30]
BTN-Re	45 mL CH_3CN , 5 mL TEOA and 10 mg	Xe lamp (400–800 nm) with	CO: 507 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[31]
viCOF-bpy-Re	Solid phase	$\lambda > 420 \text{ nm}$, 300 W Xe light source	CO: 190 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ O ₂ : 90 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[32]
TpBpy–Ru	TEOA as a sacrificial agent in acetonitrile (MeCN)	$\lambda > 400 \text{ nm}$, 300 W Xe light source	HCOOH: 271 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[33]
Re-I-SiO ₂	10 mg, 4 mL of a DMF : TEOA (3/1 v/v)	180 lamp $\lambda \geq 420 \text{ nm}$ 100 mW cm^{-2}	CO	[34]
BiVO ₄ ^a	200 mg photocatalyst, 100 mL 1.0 M NaOH solution	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420 \text{ nm}$	CH ₃ OH: 14.58 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[35]
WO ₃ ^a	100 mg photocatalyst, 0.4 mL H ₂ O	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda \geq 420 \text{ nm}$	CH ₄ : 1.16 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[36]
Bi ₂ WO ₆ /TiO ₂ ^a	Solid phase Continuous	6W lamps, $\lambda_{\text{max}}=369 \text{ nm}$, 47.23 Wm^{-2}	CH ₄ : 1.06 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[37]
1.5Ag/TiO ₂ ^a	Solid phase, Continuous	6W lamps, $\lambda_{\text{max}}=369 \text{ nm}$, 47.23 Wm^{-2}	CO: 0.7 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ CH ₄ : 5.8 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[38]
Co/CdS ^a	25 mg photocatalyst, 75 mL Na ₂ CO ₃ / Na ₂ SO ₃ solution	300 W Xe lamp $\lambda < 420 \text{ nm}$	CO: 392 $\mu\text{mol g}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$	[39]

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